

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF GAMES FOR LEARNING CHINESE

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ABSTRACT

Education has become more digitalised, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, and learning Chinese language is not an exception. Educational games, some of them based on artificial intelligence, have been designed for learning languages. This systematic review aims to examine recent (from 2017 to 2022) research published in Science Direct and Scopus databases on the use and impact of educational games, specifically in Chinese language learning. The in-depth review of 28 studies shows that games are effective tools for Chinese learning that impact students' motivation, self-efficacy progress, and learning satisfaction. However, more in-depth research should measure this impact.

KEYWORDS

Chinese language learning, games, educational games, artificial intelligence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning has become increasingly digitalised, and learning languages is not an exception. Computer games, not only educational ones, have proven to expand a learner's vocabulary, boost motivation and satisfaction, and affect interaction with peers. In most cases, games developed by researchers for classrooms or experiments are aimed at students and are effective according to pre-test and post-test results. This review thus aims to fill the literature gap and review which games are used in learning Chinese precisely and what their effects on students are, based on reviewing publications from 2017 to 2022 from databases ScienceDirect and Scopus.

The research questions are as follows:

- (1) Which games have been used so far in learning Chinese?
- (2) What characteristics (motivation, self-efficacy, progress, effectiveness, learning satisfaction) enhance games for learning Chinese?
- (3) What is the future research in this field?

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this paper represents a systematic review of the research papers from ScienceDirect and Scopus. The review was performed from 2016 to May 2022 using the following keywords: Chinese language AND game, Chinese language AND gamification. Most of the papers were found in ScienceDirect – 6 649 studies (Table 1). In the Scopus, 173 papers were detected. Thus, altogether 6822 publications were detected in two databases. Since most papers focused on the use of games in learning in general, the titles, abstracts, and introductions were reviewed, and only 26 papers focusing on Chinese language learning were analysed. Therefore, the paper was included if it matched the corresponding period, i.e., from 2016 up to

May 2022; if the intervention involved the use of a game or gamification; if it focused on the learning of Chinese language; if the study was written in English; and if it could be accessed through ScienceDirect and Scopus database. If the study was not accessible with the institutional login of Peking University, it was not included in the review. If the study was found in both databases, it was counted only once as a ScienceDirect study.

Table 1. Numbers of studies by the database and searched words.

	ScienceDirect		Scopus	
	All results	Studies selected for deeper analysis	All results	Studies selected for deeper analysis
Chinese language AND game	6377	4	155	15
Chinese language AND gamification	272	5	18	2
	6649	9	173	17

As is seen from Annex 1, most studies focus on students' motivation (five studies measure motivation specifically, but with different techniques). Seventeen studies address effectiveness, thirteen - self-efficacy, ten - students' progress, and eight - learning satisfaction. Xu et al. (2021) address all five issues. The analysis of the included studies is consistent with the previous research on games and gamification in language learning: (1) games have been actively used in Chinese language learning (2) the majority of studies address students' motivation; (3) most studies are about effectiveness, self-efficacy, students' progress, learning satisfaction. Based on the overall findings, games are compelling and motivating tools for language learning, also Chinese, but more in-depth research should measure the effect of games on students' characteristics.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

In language learning, games help to interact, and dive into the language learning environment (Chen et al., 2020). Gamification has been used in the Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) (Metwally&Yining, 2017). Studies designed for experiments in classrooms are aimed at proving gamification effectiveness, games' impact on students' motivation and attitude towards learning (Aguilar et al., 2020; Yu&Tsuei, 2022), peer learning and social interdependence (Yang et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2020), students' achievement and emotions (Lei et al., 2022). Gamification and new technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) or virtual reality may make teaching theory more exciting (Kriz et al., 2021).

Most games in language education are aimed at facilitating learning foreign languages (Su et al., 2021; Lai&Bower,2019), and only some are explicitly developed for Chinese learning (Hong et al., 2017; Wong&Hsu, 2016). Tsai et al.(2021) and Redfern & McCurry (2018) improved the Key-Image method - a novel mnemonic (memory aid) tool similar to *Chineasy* method, where characters evolve from a picture in the Chinese learning class. A similar technique was used for the *Second life* and *Sifteo cube* games by Yuan & Wang (2021). Li&Liang (2020) found that the effectiveness of games in Chinese learning comes with satisfaction from the learning process, deeper immersion, and joy in the language learning process. The collaborative mobile learning game *ToneWars* by Fan, Luo, & Wang (2017) connects Chinese learners with native speakers to improve their tone learning. The *Rensselaer Mandarin Project* in collaboration with IBM, aims at foreign language students learning Chinese in virtual reality using AI (Allen et al, 2019). Wang, Shi, & Li (2019) worked on *Wechat* mini games for Chinese learners. Poole et al. (2019) designed the *Mystery Forest* board game for Chinese learning at an elementary school in Utah,

during which students improve their Chinese language knowledge through communication with their peers. A Chinese matching game by Chen (2019) proved that teachers can design and use games in the Chinese teaching process. Jamshidifarsani et al. (2019) analysed papers related to gamification interventions. The game *Speed Mandarin* by Wang, Liu, & Zhang (2019) did not impact results from learning Chinese, but increased students' confidence in speaking. The escape-the-room game by Chou, Chang, & Hsieh (2020) on the tablets for young Chinese learners boosted their motivation and peer collaboration, although the progress of Chinese learning was hard to assess. Similar results got Cho, Andersen, & Kizilcec (2021) with their game *Delivery Ghost* for beginner learners of Mandarin. The *Questaurant* game group by Tang&Taguchi (2021) had a higher level of motivation than the online lesson group. Motivation has increased from games by Lau (2021) and (Fang&Yang, 2017) designed for classical Chinese and an ancient prose e-learning course. He&Loewen (2022) concluded that in case of low engagement in second language applications like *Memrise* teacher support is essential. Wen (2021), Fung et al.(2019) used augmented reality (AR) in the Chinese language learning games, which improved the self-learning of students and brought memorable and joyful results (Wei et al., 2020). Ying, Yulius, & Juniarto (2021), Ying et al.(2021) advocate the positive impact of the gamification of Chinese language teaching and interventions with mobile Chinese learning games.

4. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Currently, education is undergoing a digital transformation. The current review aimed to explore games for learning Chinese by reviewing 2016 to 2022 studies from ScienceDirect and Scopus databases on Chinese learning using games. 6 822 publications from ScienceDirect and Scopus databases were retrieved from which 26 publications were analysed in detail. A few studies focus specifically on learning Chinese as a foreign language through games. Games described in the current review that might be useful to Chinese learners are: *Chineasy*, *Chinese-PP*, *Delivery Ghost*, *escape-the-room*, *Key-Image*, *Memrise*, *Mystery Forest Newby*, *Questaurant*, *Rensselaer Mandarin Project*, *Second life*, *Sifteo cube*.

While previous research has established the effectiveness of games without focusing on Chinese language, this study specifically reviews games for Chinese learning. The review of studies shows that the majority of authors focus on students' motivation, self-efficacy, students 'achievements, learning effectiveness, or satisfaction, but a few measure them. Hopefully, this study may encourage researchers to reflect upon the different impacts games make on students, broaden their research questions to several characteristics enhanced by games, and not only describe but also measure the effect of games on students.

There are several limitations to this study. First, this review covered studies only from two databases – ScienceDirect and Scopus. Although there are the highest quality journals, but their number is limited. Secondly, the review is limited by a five-year time frame, from 2017 to 2022. Although the analysis is most relevant to new games, but there could possibly be more analysis made before 2017. Thirdly, reviewed studies are in English. Although some researchers are Chinese, but there is a high possibility that a lot of research on Chinese learning is done in Mandarin or other languages. Finally, only motivation, self-efficacy, students 'achievements, learning effectiveness or satisfaction, and progress are reviewed in this study, but the impact of games on students is much broader.

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Annex 1. Literature Review

Author	Game/ITS	Methodology	Motivation	Self-efficacy	Progress	Effectiveness	Learning satisfaction
Tsai et al.(2021)	Chinese radical (key)-image method	Achievement test, inventory	increased	N/A, but efficiency & efficacy increased			
Li&Liang (2020)	Chinese learning effectiveness	Surveys				0.807	0.802
Fan, Luo, & Wang (2017)	Acquiring Chinese tones through games	Pre- and post-test, survey, interview	gained through confidence			proved	present
Allen et al.(2019)	Rensselaer Mandarin Project learning & virtual travel (in development)	Descriptive creation of the game		self-govern			
Wang, Shi, & Li (2019)	Chinese Language Learning in WeChat Mini programs	Descriptive creation of the game				aimed at, but not measured	
Poole et al.(2019)	Collaborative board game	Audio collection & analysis	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured		aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured
Chen (2019)	Chinese matching game	Descriptive creation of the game	aimed at, but not measured				
Jamshidifarsaniet al.(2019)	Technology-based reading intervention programs	Literature review	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	
Wang, Liu, & Zhang (2019)	Speed Mandarin computer program	Pre- and post-questionnaire	3.46-3.5	aimed at, but not measured		measured through competences	
Chou, Chang, & Hsieh (2020)	Escape-the-room game with tablets	Pre- and post-test, interview	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured		aimed at, but not measured	

Tang&Taguchi (2021)	Questaurant game	Recognition & production test, questionnaire	61.33 for game players vs 52 for no players		mentioned in the questionnaire	aimed at, but not measured	mentioned in the questionnaire
Lau (2021)	E-learning activities in Classic Chinese reading	Pre- and post-questionnaire	3.19-3.78	3.13-3.43		aimed at, but not measured	
Fang&Yang, 2017	Avatars and Learning Companions in Studying Chinese Classical Literature	Pre- and post-questionnaire	aimed at, but not measured				
He&Loewen (2022)	Memrise	Pre- and post-questionnaire, survey	boosted by 34%			supported	
Cho, Andersen, &Kizilcec (2021)	Delivery Ghost	Pre- and post-questionnaire, survey	interactivity and immersion are less critical to learning at the beginner-level than a well-structured curriculum				
Wen Wen (2018)	Augmentedrealityenhancedchinesecharacterlearninggame	Recorded learning process, focus group discussions	engagement	aimed at improved self-learning, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured		
Fung, Fung, & Wan (2019)	Augmented reality and 3D model for children Chinese character recognition	Pre- and post-test, teacher & student focus groups	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at improved self-learning, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured		

Wei et al. (2020)	Mobile AR Language Learning Environment Based on Virtual avatar	Pre- and post-test, questionnaire	measured as learning attitude in min, higher with AR (10 min)				higher with AR (4.58 vs 3)
Ying, Yulius, & Juniarto (2020)	Chinese learning listening games	Questionnaires	aimed at, but not measured		aimed at, but not measured		
Ying et al. (2020)	Mandamonic games	Surveys	aimed at, but not measured			aimed at, but not measured	
Chen et al., 2020	Games, ITS powered by AI, e.g. Korbit	Literature review	mentioned in 0.91% publications	mentioned in 0.48% publications			
Serban et al., 2020	Korbit	Questionnaires	aimed at, but not measured		average student learning measured as correct answers with pedagogical interventions 39.14%	effective pedagogical interventions	"fun" according to students
Bhutoria (2022)	A systematic review of personalized Edtech using AI in the US, China, India	Literature review	aimed at, but not measured			aimed at, but not measured	
Kashyap, 2021	Chinese room argument	Literature review	aimed at, but not measured		aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured

Wang, 2015	Cross-device mobile-assisted classical chinese learning system fo flipped classroom	Question naires	enhanced to 4 in comparison to 3.33	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	
Xu et al., 2021	Chinese character online instruction	Question naires	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured
Goksu, 2021	Bibliometric mapping of mobile learning	Literature review	aimed at, but not measured			aimed at, but not measured	
Hong et al., 2017	Game correcting writing in Chinese	Question naire	aimed at, but not measured	aimed at, but not measured			